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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION OF INGREDIENTS OF CHATURUSHANA

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Abstract

Background: Ayurvedic medicine is considered to be world's oldest medical system, which is originated in India thousands of years ago. According to Ayurveda, we have an abundance of knowledge regarding the use of therapeutic plants from ancient times. For thousands of years, plants have contributed significantly to the well-being and health of humans. They are also important sources of essential ingredients for pharmaceuticals, beverages, cosmetics, and medicines. Powder microscopy is a component of pharmacognosy which helps in both medicine originality and impurity detection. For the majority of preparations, powders are used frequently. The method of evaluating and standardizing herbal powder by powder microscopy ultimately results in the herbal drug's authentication. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Chaturushana* was carried out. *Chaturushana Churna* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Marich* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Pipalimool* (*Piper longum* Linn.) and *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). Slides of each ingredient of *Chaturushana* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Chaturushana Churna* shows reticulate xylem vessels and parenchyma, fibers, fragments of metaderm, fragments of thin-walled cells, acicular crystals, epidermal cells, oil cells, cork, phloem parenchyma, starch grains etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Chaturushana* helps in the correct identification of *Marich* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Pipalimool* (*Piper longum* Linn.) and *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). Powder microscopy is one of the easiest methods which helps in quality control and assurance of herbal drug.

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Key Words:

Powder microscopy, *Chaturushana*, *Marich* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Pipalimool* (*Piper longum* Linn.) and *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.).

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, the medications are chosen based on their *Gunas* (properties) In Ayurveda, the *Dravyas* have various dimensions. In Ayurveda, altogether are designed taking into consideration a diverse number of aspects. In present era, due to high demand of the herbal drugs, adulteration and substitution is commonly seen by the pharmaceutical companies and traders. So, to keep a check on this and to achieve good therapeutic efficacy, Pharmacognosy plays an important role. One of the simplest techniques for accurately identifying an herbal medicine is powder microscopy. It supports assurance and quality control for herbal medications. Additionally, it helps in standardizing the novel medication, preparing it for marketing purposes.

Chaturushana Churna formulation containing *Marich* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Pipalimool* (*Piper longum* Linn.) and *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). *Chaturushana Churna* is the compound Ayurvedic formulations prescribed in the management of indigestion. Pharmacognostical study accounting powder microscopy of raw drug exposed the quality and genuineness of all the constituents of *Churna*.

Importance of present study: Substances differ in their *Gunas* (attributes) which reflects through the physical as well as chemical properties. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India has already developed the standards for single drugs i.e. *Shunthi*, *Maricha*, *Pippali*, *Pippalimoola* of this compound. Hence, attempts have been made for development of preliminary pharmacognostical profile of *Chaturushana Churna* (mixture of these six) before its administration and comparison pharmacognostical properties of *Chaturushana Churna*.

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Chaturushana*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as fibres, tissues, vascular bundles, starch grains, trichomes etc. in the powder of *Marich* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), *Pipalimool* (*Piper longum* Linn.) and *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.).
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

3. *Chaturushana* was used for the powder microscopy. *Chaturushana* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Marich* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.), *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.), and roots of *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.) and rhizome of *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Chaturushan* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.¹⁻⁴

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Chaturushana Churna*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Marich</i>	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Pipalimool</i>	<i>Sunthi</i>
1.	Fragments of fibres		+	+	+

2.	Tissue cell		+	+	+
3.	Vessel element				+
5.	Starch Grains		+		+
6.	Oil cell				+
7.	Crystal				
8.	Stone cell		+		
9.	Tracheids			+	
10.	Sclereids			+	
11.	Hyaline layer	+			
12.	Beaker cells	+			
13.	Spiral vessels	+			
14.	Volatile oil cell	+			
15.	Pigment layer	+			
16.	Epicarp cells	+			

Table No. 2: Powder microscopic study of *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Marich</i>	Figure no.
1.	Hyaline layer	Fig. 1.a
2.	Beaker cells	Fig. 1.b
3.	Spiral vessels	Fig. 1.c
4.	Volatile oil cell	Fig. 1.d
5.	Pigment layer	Fig. 1.e
6.	Epicarp cells	Fig. 1.f

Table No. 3: Powder microscopic study of *Pippali* (*Piper longum* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pippali</i>	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	Fig. 2.a
2.	Starch grains	Fig. 2.b
3.	Fragments of thin-walled cells	Fig. 2.c
4.	Fibres	Fig. 2.d

Table No. 4: Powder microscopic study of *Pipalimool* (*Piper longum* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Pipalimool</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fibres	Fig. 3.a
2.	Scleroids	Fig. 3.b
3.	Cork in surface view	Fig. 3.c
4.	Group of trechoids	Fig. 3.d

Table No.5 : Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sunthi</i>	Figure no.
2.	Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell	Fig. 4.a
4.	Starch grains	Fig. 4.b
5.	Reticulated vessel with pigment cell	Fig. 4.c
6.	Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains	Fig. 4.d
7.	Fragment of fiber with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel	Fig. 4.e

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Chaturushana* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Chaturushana* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Marich* shows, epicarp cells in surface view, hyaline layer, beaker cell, spiral vessels, volatile oil cell and pigment layer. Powder microscopy of *Pippali* shows stone cell, starch grains, fragments of thin-walled cells and fibers. Powder microscopy of *Pippalimool* shows, Fibres, Scleroids, Cork in surface view and Group of trechoids. Powder microscopy of *Shunthi* shows, Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell, Starch grains, Reticulated vessel with pigment cell, Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains and Fragment of fibre with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel. Standardization of compound Ayurvedic formulations is quite difficult and complicated. But it is necessary to ensure the quality and safety of herbal drugs which makes herbal medicines very useful. In this present study, powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Chaturushana* was carried out and their microscopic characters were noted. These characters might help in detecting impurities and exact identification of material available from the market.

Powder microscopic study of *Marich*

[Fig. 1.a]

[Fig. 1.b]

[Fig. 1.c]

[Fig. 1.d]

[Fig. 1.d]

[Fig. 1.e]

Epicarp cells

Powder microscopic study of *Pippali*

Stone cell

[Fig. 2.a]

Starch grains

[Fig. 2.b]

Fragments of thin-walled cell

[Fig. 2.c]

Fibre

[Fig. 2.d]

Phai

Powder microscopic study of *Pippalimool*

Fibers

[Fig. 3.a]

Sclereids

[Fig. 3.b]

Cork in surface view

[Fig. 3.c]

Group of tracheids

[Fig. 3.d]

Powder microscopic study of *Shunthi*

Oleoresin cell

[Fig. 4.a]

Starch grains

[Fig. 4.b]

Reticulated
Vessel with
pigment cell

Cortical
parenchyma
containing
starch grains

[Fig. 4.d]

Fragment of fibre
with attached
parenchyma and
reticulated vessel

[Fig. 4.e]

CONCLUSION:

Powder microscopy helps to find out the impurities and also helps in quality assessment of the drug. To standardize and evaluate herbal powder and thus provides means for assessing the authenticity and morality of herbal drugs. The current study's findings aid in the identification of herbal formulations like *Chaturushana*. , Epicarp cells in surface view ,hyaline layer, beaker cell, spiral vessels ,volatile oil cell and pigment layer these structures are indicating presence of *Marich (Piper nigrum Linn.)*; Stone cell, starch grains, fragments of thin-walled cells and fibers these structures are indicating presence of *Pippali(Piper longum Linn.)*; Fibers, scleroids, cork in surface view and Group of trechoids are indicating *Pippalimool (Piper longum Linn.)*;and cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell ,Starch grains, Reticulated vessel with pigment cell, Cortical parenchyma containing starch grains and Fragment of fibre with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel are indicating presence of *Sunthi (Zingiber officinale Rose.)* in *Chaturushana*.

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